

**GULISTAN
STATE
UNIVERSITY**

PERSPECTIVES OF PHILOLOGY AND PRACTICAL POSSIBILITIES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

**PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

GULISTAN, OCTOBER 16-17, 2024

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BALIKESIR UNIVERSITY (TURKEY)

KAZAN FEDERAL UNIVERSITY (RUSSIA)

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OLIV TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI

GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI (O'ZBEKISTON)

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**FILOLOGIYA ISTIQBOLLARI
VA CHET TILLAR O'QITISHNING
AMALIY IMKONIYATLARI**

XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENTSIYA MATERIALLARI

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“O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish kontsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublika Prezidentining 5847-sonli Farmonida ko‘zda tutilgan vazifalardan biri – ilmiy izlanish yutuklarini amaliyotga joriy etish yo‘li bilan fan sohalarini rivojlantirish, ya’ni xalqaro ilmiy hamjamiyatda e’tirof etilishiga xizmat qilishdir. Konferentsiyani o‘tkazish uchun asosi – O‘zbekiston Respublika Prezidentining 19 may 2021 yildagi 5117-sonli “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida xorijiy tillarni o‘rganishni ommalashtirish faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” qarori, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 4 iyul 2023 yildagi PQ-200 "Ma'muriy islohotlar doirasida oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar sohasida davlat boshqaruvini samarali tashkil etish chora-tadbirlarni to'g'risida" qarori va O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirining 18 yanvar 2024 yil 16-sonli buyrug‘i (2024 yilda xalqaro miqyosida o‘tkaziladigan ilmiy va texnik tadbirlar rejasi, №174). Shu va boshqa tegishli farmonlarda va qarorlarda belgilangan vazifalarini amalga oshirish maqsadida **2024 yil 16-17 oktabrda** Guliston davlat universiteti “Ingliz tili va adabiyoti” kafedrasidan “**Filologiya istiqbollari va chet tillar o‘qitishning amaliy imkoniyatlari**” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyasi o‘tkazilgan. Konferentsiya zamonaviy filologiya fanining eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzularini va uslubiy ishlanmalarini aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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To‘plamga kiritilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlarning to‘g‘riligi hamda fikr-mulohazalar, keltirilgan takliflarga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar.

ISAAC ASIMOV'S SCIENCE FICTION: THE STRUCTURAL DIVISION OF THE GENRE

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Abstract. The article deals with the problem of structural division of science fiction genre on the example of works written by American author Isaac Asimov. The article includes scientific substantiation of the genre's initial division into 'hard' and 'soft' science fiction, explanation of the main characteristics of each subdivision, and provides suitable examples from Isaac Asimov's works.

Keywords: genre, science fiction, Isaac Asimov, 'hard' science fiction, 'soft' science fiction.

Unique features of science fiction as a literary genre lie in its general classification and divisions or "sub-genres".

It is generally accepted to consider a work of fiction as authentic when it reflects the real world with observation. However, there is a certain reality that can be revealed only by means of scientific or technical knowledge. This is the case of *hard SF* which is defined as "the form of imaginative literature that uses either established or carefully extrapolated science as its backbone" [1,9]. The themes of this sub-genre include subjects related to astrophysics, computer technologies, robotics, cybernetics, gravity, mathematics, space flight and spaceships, power sources. This sub-genre require not to rely on real scientific accuracy but to depict a world that science and technology might make accessible; that is, it should respect the scientific spirit and principles that provide natural rather than supernatural explanation of the phenomena. The most prominent figures of hard SF include R.Heinlein, I.Asimov, and P.Anderson.

In contrast to hard SF, *soft SF* deals with themes related to soft sciences: the social sciences (economics, sociology, anthropology, linguistics, psychology) which are concerned with human affairs and societies and which focus on human feelings that require neither technological hardware nor physical laws for their carrying out. Soft SF is also used as a synonym for New Wave SF, that tried to bring SF into mainstream and had a strong involvement in the late 1960's counterculture, focusing on the likelihood of disaster caused by social, ecological and political factors [2,34]. Among the most prominent writers of this sub-genre are R.Bradbury, U.Le Guin, and B.Aldiss.

Space opera occupies a quite particular place in SF and has the focus on action-adventure interstellar travel and space battles and wars. Its main storyline is interplanetary conflict in which the writers portray characters using mystical powers and destroying whole planets and alien species. According to critics, the stories of space opera are interpreted as a speculation about future war in space and its effects on humans [3,12]. Among the outstanding practitioners of this genre are S.Baxter, D.Weber, and I.Asimov, especially in his Foundation Series.

Utopia, as a SF sub-genre, has come to mean an ideal world to be achieved by the efforts of human beings based on scientific and technological progress. Another variant is the shift from dealing with a better place to dealing with a better time under the influence of historical and social change and progress [4,171]. In recent years, a more pessimistic outlook has given birth to *dystopian* SF in which the actual world's problems have been aggravated by overpopulation, the prospects of pollution and the destruction of the environment. Among the notable writers who adopted the dystopian trend are R.Bradbury in "Fahrenheit 451", I.Asimov in "The Caves of Steel", K.Vonnegut in "Harrison Bergeron", and R.Heinlein in "Sixth Column".

Thus, modern literary critics distinguish 4 basic sub-genres of SF – with their specific traits and characteristics.

However, Isaac Asimov has advocated the idea that science fiction is a flavour that can be applied to any genre of fiction. The two novels "The Naked Sun" and "The Robots of Dawn" are in keeping with this idea. The two stories are essentially whodunit stories, with several futuristic technologies like positronic robots and hyperspace travel blended into it. Such futuristic technology stories, which take place in a world completely unfamiliar to the reader, fit into models of classification described by Tzvetan Todorov and Arthur

Asa Berger. The notion of 'crime and punishment' is handled differently in these stories, and elements of science fiction and futuristic technologies fit into the genre of detective fiction. The two novels are set in the same universe as Asimov's former short story series "I, Robot", although the former is set in a period around two thousand years in the future. As Asimov writes in the introduction to "The Naked Sun", it was his Horace Gold, the editor of *Galaxy*, who suggested Asimov to write a robot novel following the success of his short stories featuring positronic robots. Though Gold's original suggestion was to write a novel with a sociological theme, set in an overpopulated world in which robots were taking over jobs, Asimov was able to successfully merge this theme into a thriller futuristic technologies story.

As mentioned in the introduction, Asimov was told that science fiction mysteries would not play fair with the reader. To prevent this 'potential cheating of the readers', Asimov proposed the following rules (in the introduction to Asimov's "Mysteries"); that the writer shouldn't spring new devices on the reader and solve the mystery with them and that the writer shouldn't take advantage of future history to introduce ad hoc phenomena. All facets of the future background should be explained well in advance so that the reader gets a decent chance to see the solution. The detective should make use of only the facts which are known to the reader in the present, or the 'facts' of the fictional future which are explained beforehand. Asimov says that if these rules are accepted, it becomes obvious that science fiction mystery is a thoroughly acceptable literary form.

In the introduction to Asimov's "Mysteries", he writes that science fiction shouldn't be classified as a member of the group of specialised literatures, but that it is a literary response to scientific change in which that "science fiction includes everything".

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LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN THE AGE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: STRUCTURES, GENRES, PERCEPTION AND CRITICISM

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Abstract. The digital age as any type of technological breakthrough tends to be accompanied by anxious announcements of its effect on language and literature. In fact, digital gadgets change both the process of creating books and reading culture. Social media and e-platforms make it easier for people to access and discuss literary works. Consequently, the digital age produces new frameworks that adjust the ways in which language and literature exists.

Keywords: digital age, language, literature, structure, genre, perception, criticism.

Introduction. In recent decades, we have seen the rapid advancement of digital technology, which has had a significant impact on many aspects of life, including language and literature. The Internet, social media, mobile applications, and other technologies have altered not only communication methods, but also the fundamental nature of language structures, literary genres, and forms. Digitalization opens up new avenues for text creation and perception, as well as challenging traditional notions of literary work and authorship. This paper investigates key aspects of digital technology's impact on language and literature, as well as the prospects for future development.

1. Changes in language structure and vocabulary. Language has undergone significant changes as a result of digital technologies, particularly in terms of lexicon. New terms and abbreviations have emerged as the norm in Internet users' communication. Many abbreviations, including 'LOL', 'BRB', and 'OMG', have become commonplace, particularly among young people. Emoji and stickers used in messengers and social networks act as additional expressive tools, replacing words and creating new levels of meaning. Modern

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